

THE IMPACT OF USING ICT ON TEACHING EFL LEARNERS

Buranova Nasiba

Teacher of English of academic lyceum of SSU

Nurmukhammedova Iroda

Teacher of English of academic lyceum of SSU

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ANNOTATION

The current article is devoted to study the influence of using ICT devices and the interests of students for learning foreign languages. It informs about the results of usage modern methods by the help of ICTs and the roles of IC tools, their importance as well as features of contemporary technologies.

The article tries to highlight on utilizing ICTs can improve fast and easily learners' four main skills such as writing, speaking, listening and reading, as well as to motivate and encourage students to learn the target language.

ICTs are new tools for learning and teaching English

It is visible that nowadays information and communication technologies (ICT) take essential and vital role in all spheres of human's life and in the world, especially in the educational process and in the teaching and learning foreign languages (FL). ICTs have been introduced and known in schools and institutions during the last decade and it's compulsory to use ICTs in teaching in many countries' educational process. There are number of definition for the term of ICT, as Information communication technology or technologies are modern and different tools to communicate, to gather and share, create, manage and store information. ICTs include television, radio, phones, computer, internet and network hardware and software. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) cover a wider range of technologies such as radio, television, computers, the Internet, social networks and many other variations of technology.

According to UNESCO, ICT defines as technologies that are used in order to transmit, process, store, create, display, share or exchange information by electronic means. As it is known that ICTs are used in all fields of life, as ICT in industry, ICT in law, ICT in medicine, ICT in science, ICT in education and so on. Nowadays ICTs are assisting tools and tools for organization and management in schools and institutions.

It is fact that, in the 1980's one of the well-known language program Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) gave a chance to teachers and learners of foreign languages through using of CD-ROMs to enrich their language level.

It should be noticed that ICTs have strong and significant role in education, if ICTs' users utilize devices under right conditions, ICT may support teaching and learning, give new opportunities for interaction among teachers, students and knowledge; accessing, manipulating, storing and sharing information as well as create new and fertile atmosphere in education process.

21st century is the period of IC technologies and it can give a chance for people work and study at home as distance learning or study in two or more institutions at the same time. As ICT can shorten distance, e-banking and e-government are now possible from any place with an Internet connection and a computing device.

ICT, such as the internet can provide with a great deal of opportunities language teachers and learners, as learners can interact or communicate with other culture people by the help of ICT and in the target language which they are learning as foreign or second language. During the lessons they may utilize class projectors, video chats or video calls with Skype and other software, which are increasing day by day. As scientist in Taiwan Young states that Internationalisation, communication with other cultures, is important in modern society language teaching. The use of Internet had a positive effect in the sense that learners were able to communicate with other countries making connections with other learners. Furthermore, he states that one of the reasons why Internet is to be used in education is because it puts English in an international context .

As it goes without saying that teaching and learning were considered as face to face process and not long time ago teachers were in the centre, especially in teaching foreign languages. Pupils could not learn the FL without the help of the teachers. The teacher had to explain the theme in traditional way and pupils consolidated previous materials and repeated new vocabulary with their teacher, in order not to mistake while pronouncing sounds and words. However, nowadays as the result of developing ICTs as new tools, teachers' role in the classroom and in teaching process is somehow different. In 21st century, teachers' role is as a mentor, an observer and a guide to knowledge instead of the traditional teacher. Fitzpatrick writes about teachers as "facilitators" of knowledge and that teachers need to be aware of the different ways of using ICT in order to improve learners' language skills .

ICTs are new and essential tools that can support teachers during lessons. Technologies can improve lesson design and help to teachers to run lessons interestingly, transform teaching and learning, as well as engage and motivate pupils to learn more effectively. ICTs take essential part for students and language learners for their critical thinking. And it has chance for making drafts and plans, if there are any mistakes laptops as main components or tools of the ICTs, can easily correct at once or may give some advice while writing on computers, as well as improve learners' writing skills. Modern technologies provide structured opportunities for improving speaking and listening skills of students. It goes without doubt that ICTs are good helpers for learners in order to present and share their ideas more effectively and in different ways by the help of various tools of ICTs.

It is claimed that ICT is as a new tool considered as a teacher – teaches learners a new language, demonstrates and helps the way of learning. ICT is a tester or examiner that tests students on the already learned structures and a main tool for doing certain tasks, a data source which learners and teachers can easily get and find necessary information, as well as it is as a communication tool that provides students to communicate with others.

As it is obvious that ICT as a new tool can change both teachers' and learners' roles in the classroom as some ages ago teachers were in the center of teaching and learning process, had a great role in education, he was a knowledge provider, a director and a controller all aspects of learning, however the use of ICT in education brings some changes in teacher roles. Nowadays teachers are as observers, demonstrators the correct way for learners, cooperators, knowledge navigators, information giver, pupil-manager and give learners more options and responsibilities for their own learning. Students are in the centre of the teaching and learning process.

As it is undoubted, there are number of ICTs' components that are considered as vital and necessary tools for every field of life and education as well.

One of the most vital components of ICTs is the internet, as Moore (2005) argues that the Internet is a research tool in schools; it is used by the students to find their own information by their own . The internet is the large system of connected computers around the world which allows people to share information and communicate with each other. Nowadays most of schools use the Internet extensively for research and gathering ideas, and even for interacting directly with other organizations via their websites. The Internet as a new teaching tool has a great number of advantages and benefits for teachers and learners, such as the internet is an ocean of information so we can find any materials in many ways with a fast speed. Learning and teaching processes are interesting with materials, activities and games which are given from the net. Nowadays news and information can be changed or updated at any time, with the help of the internet we can easily find or be aware of them.

Computer is a programmable electronic device that performs mathematical calculations and logical operations, especially it can process, store and retrieve large amounts of data very quickly, it helps to manipulate or type texts, graphics, access the internet, play games or media. With the invention and introduction of the computer, learning and teaching are not so long and difficult processes for both teachers and learners. Nowadays teachers utilize computers, notebooks, laptops for typing their every day's plans, storing e-books rather than keeping or handing many books with themselves in every lesson.

Television is one of the major IC technologies and it is older than other information devices as the radio. As there are a lot of programs for learning FL for people who want to learn through satellite and terrestrial television programs. There are not only contemporary and authentic programs but also potentially culturally rich programs for the language learners. In Uzbekistan there are about 15 or 20 channels however only 4 channels have special programs for language learners, there are debates about any themes, some teaching language classes, nature and historical programs and teaching kids for children in English. Some cartoons and films are given in FL for children in order to motivate them for learning language.

Nowadays audio devices are mostly used in language classes in order to enhance pupils' listening skills. Audio devices as CDs, Web and audiocassette recorders are considered as modern and important tools for improving lessons.

"Video (also videotape) is a recording of moving pictures and sound that has been made on a long narrow strip of magnetic material inside a rectangular plastic container, and which can be played on a special machine so that it can be watched on television" (Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary 3rd Edition). We can find videos in DVD, cassette, Web, laserdisc, camera. Thanks to modern technology that moving images and sounds in videos can provide language learners with all important elements of verbal and non-verbal communication as body language, gestures, postures, facial expressions, proxemics, pronunciation, intonation. Nowadays films and video sequences are dubbed in both target language and mother tongue as well as there are sub-titles and texts in order to understand the meaning of the given context in the video. Videos can help learners to improve their language skills as listening and speaking as well.

Most of people think that a telephone as a new tool is not so helpful or crucial for language learning, using of a telephone is limited in education, it may have little support to teach learners as for only conference calls. However, nowadays modern mobile and smart phones are easily taking places of computers and laptops with their universal functions. With the help of phones people can do many things not only speaking on the telephone, face-to-face communication, but also they utilize in order to looking for words from the electronic dictionaries, reading e-books, searching information from the net and storing important materials and information, calculating, taking pictures, listening audio materials, watching video materials, films, cartoons and so on.

Video conference or conferencing is when two or more people who are in different parts of the world can talk, to each other and see each other on television screens. "VC can be a tool for improving student outcomes through meeting more needs of the diverse body of students by opening up possibilities for clarification, negotiation and thoughtful evaluation of teaching and learning".

In education process video conference is very important that if you cannot take part in real conference but it is very necessary for you, you can easily connect through IC technologies and you can participate in video conference even in abroad. According to famous linguists, as Panteli and Dawson (2001) argue that VC is a powerful tool that educators can use to share and deliver instruction, it can also reduce barriers such as travel safety, costs, and time that may impede trips for interviews, visits to potential job sites and conference designs for intellectual exchanges.

Nowadays tremendous changes are observed in different fields of life, especially in education it is visible through IC technologies. Some centuries ago there were black boards which used with chalks, and afterwards white boards have been used with the help of special colorful markers, today interactive whiteboards (IWBs) or electronic boards are invented and it is very easy to draw pupils' attention to the lessons and participate actively as well as engage more students in the lesson. Interactive whiteboards are new and useful tools that provide with great opportunities such as different kinds of multimedia resources. According to the British Educational Communications and Technology Agency IWBs are defined as following:

“An interactive whiteboard is a large, touch-sensitive which is connected to a digital projector and a computer. The projector displays the image from the computer screen on the board. The computer can then be controlled by touching the board, either directly or with a special pen. The potential applications are: using web-based resources in whole-class teaching, showing video clips to help explain concepts, presenting students' work to the rest of the classroom, creating digital flipcharts, manipulating text and practicing handwriting, and saving notes on the board for future use” .

We can easily use special pen or our finger around a large touch-sensitive electronic board in order to move objects on the board.

Undoubtedly, utilizing IC technologies in education creates new, fun, friendly and effective as well as successful teaching and learning environment. There are numerous components of ICT, however every of them has own functions and advantages. ICT tools differ from each other according to its uses. In teaching and learning English as a foreign language (EFL) or English as a second language (ESL) ICT is important as breathing.

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